

SOCIAL FACTORS AFFECTING LONGEVITY

Abdiraimova Sh.A.,

Junior Researcher, Research Institute "Family and Gender"

shakhnoza.abdiraimova@mail.ru

Annotation. *This article analyzes various factors of longevity. Factors affecting longevity, in particular, sports and interesting activities, health and spirituality, walking in a cheerful mood, keeping clean, getting knowledge, etc., are discussed in detail. The final part contains a summary and a list of used literature.*

Keywords. *Longevity, sports, health, learning, rules of hygiene, psyche, mood, factors.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются различные факторы долголетия. Подробно рассмотрены факторы, влияющие на долголетие, в частности, занятия спортом и интересными занятиями, здоровье и духовность, прогулки в хорошем настроении, соблюдение чистоты, получение знаний и т.д. Заключительная часть содержит резюме и список использованной литературы.*

Ключевые слова. *Долголетие, спорт, здоровье, обучение, правила гигиены, психика, настроение, факторы.*

Annatatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada uzoq umr ko'rishning turli omillari tahlil qilingan. Uzoq umr ko'rishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar xususan, sport va qiziqarli mashg'ulotlar bilan shug'llanish, salomatlik va ruhiyat, ko'tarinki kayfiyatda yurish, tozalikka rioya qilish, bilim olish kabilarga batafsil to'xtalib o'tilgan. Yakuniy qismda xulosa va foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar. *Uzoq umr ko'rish, sport, salomatlik, bilim olish, gigena qoidalari, ruhiyat, kayfiyat, omillar.*

INTRODUCTION

Various studies are being conducted worldwide to explore the factors that contribute to longevity. For example, in Japan, the average life expectancy for women is 87 years, while for men it is 81 years. Many factors contribute to longevity in Japan, including adherence to a healthy lifestyle (strictly following nutrition guidelines, engaging in sports, maintaining hygiene practices), sticking to a regular daily routine, and undergoing routine medical check-ups.

Spain has also achieved high levels of longevity. One of the key factors contributing to longevity in Spain is the Mediterranean diet, which includes a high intake of fruits, fish, and vegetables. These factors are considered crucial for promoting long life.

Studying the factors that influence longevity and applying them in daily life can help extend life expectancy. To maintain good health, people regularly visit medical institutions, where healthcare professionals provide advice on preserving health and explain the key factors of longevity.

Throughout their lives, individuals may encounter stressful situations, depression, and anxiety, which can lead to various health problems. These health issues can negatively affect life expectancy. Preventing such problems and applying the necessary factors for longevity is essential for improving overall well-being and extending lifespan.

Literature Review. According to research conducted by experts, people, various communities, and groups continuously strive for a peaceful life, good living standards, and material prosperity. Additionally, they regularly visit health centers to maintain their well-being.

It is important to enhance knowledge and skills regarding the factors influencing longevity throughout one's life. Living with a partner is also considered a key factor for longevity. On the other hand, living alone negatively affects health and can lead to a shorter lifespan. It is essential to explore the factors contributing to longevity and ensure that every individual lives a happy and meaningful life. Below, we will examine some of the factors that influence longevity:

Engaging in sports and interesting activities. Engaging in interesting activities can significantly improve a person's mood, which, in turn, contributes to the potential for a longer life. The role of sports in life holds great importance, as it promotes both mental and physical well-being. Research conducted by several scientists shows that participating in enjoyable activities, such as sports, offers considerable health benefits. The study findings suggest that participating in group activities or doing sports with a partner can help extend life expectancy. However, certain types of sports can also be beneficial when practiced individually. Therefore, it would be incorrect to conclude that one should always avoid engaging in sports alone¹.

In rural areas, residents are frequently engaged in daily household tasks and physical activities. Such constant movement contributes to forming a healthy lifestyle and has a positive effect on the circulatory system. Regular physical activity and being

¹ <https://daryo.uz/2022/10/25/inson-umrini-uzaytirishga-yordam-beradigan-sport-turlari>

involved in productive work are beneficial for extending life expectancy and maintaining good health.

Health and well-being. Health issues affect individuals at all ages, and everyone regardless of age should take care of their health. Health problems that arise at different stages of life can significantly impact a person's longevity. Therefore, it is important to focus on preventing and managing health issues. When any health concerns arise, people visit healthcare centers for advice and support, ensuring that the situation improves.

Stress and mental well-being. Nearly everyone experiences stress, frustration, anxiety, hopelessness, or depressive feelings at some point in life. These challenges can vary in intensity. The key is not to let stress, anger, or anxiety take over, but to seek constructive solutions. If these situations are handled positively, they can lead to improved well-being; however, ignoring them can lead to negative outcomes.

Research findings show that even mild stress can result in headaches, difficulty relaxing, loss of appetite, back pain, and other health concerns. To prevent these issues, it's important to explore preventive measures and provide helpful advice. Addressing mental and emotional challenges is an essential factor in maintaining overall health and promoting a longer life.

Maintaining a positive mood. According to research conducted by practicing psychologists, consistently maintaining a positive mood is an important factor in promoting longevity. In a study carried out over 30 years, involving 70,000 individuals, researchers examined their health and lifestyle. The findings revealed that people who maintained a cheerful and happy attitude tended to live longer compared to those who experienced frequent mood downturns².

Follow the rules of hygiene - the basis of a healthy life. Maintaining cleanliness plays an important role in ensuring human health and well-being. Following the rules of hygiene helps prevent infections, improve health, maintain energy and improve overall life.

Personal hygiene, such as washing hands regularly, taking a shower, keeping nails clean and wearing clean clothes - not only improves appearance, but also supports internal health. Maintaining cleanliness also helps reduce stress and maintain mental health.

In order to live a long and healthy life, it is necessary to pay attention to personal hygiene, as well as general cleanliness. Maintaining cleanliness in public places also helps to avoid environmental pollution and protect nature.

² <https://qvz.uz/qiziq/yaxshi-kayfiyatda-bolish-uzoq-umr-korishga-yordam-beradi.html>

Maintaining hygiene is a key factor in preventing diseases, maintaining health and living a prosperous life.

Learning is the basis of a long and prosperous life. There is no age limit to learning. The more knowledge is acquired, the more skills are developed, and this serves to ensure the well-being of society. Today, the opportunities for learning are very wide, everyone has the opportunity to obtain the necessary knowledge to achieve their goals.

Learning also increases interest in life, strengthens a person's confidence in life. From the younger generation to the older generation, the desire to learn increases the potential for longevity. Older people also increase their interest in their lives through learning, and this leads to an improvement in life expectancy.

The comprehensive benefits of learning not only ensure personal development, but also enrich professional activities, and have a positive impact on those around them. The population's desire for knowledge helps to give the future generation the right direction and increases interest in science and development in society.

Thus, gaining knowledge is the most important factor that not only improves the quality of life, but also helps to live a long, healthy and prosperous life. Gaining knowledge is the basis of a prosperous life and longevity!

CONCLUSION

The various factors studied above contribute to the population living a healthy lifestyle and living a long life. The population should constantly adhere to a healthy lifestyle, be attentive to health, and undergo a medical examination every 6 months. Regularly engaging in activities and sports that raise the mood that a person likes improves mood and, as a result, leads to a long life. In addition, from the factors that cause a person to live longer, observing the rules of cleanliness, hygiene, spending free time meaningfully, and gaining knowledge lead to very effective results. Adhering to sleep standards. If attention is paid to the norm and quality of good sleep, a person's internal organs will fully rest, if a person does not get enough sleep, blood circulation and the functioning of internal organs will be impaired. Also, adhering to healthy eating standards. It is necessary to eat more vegetables, meat and easily digestible nutritious products. It is necessary to strictly adhere to the 3-meal diet per day. It is strictly forbidden to eat harmful products.

REFERENCES

1. Ageing in the twenty-first century: a celebration and a challenge. NY: UNFPA, 2012. - 192 p.
2. Abduramanov X.X. O‘zbekistonda aholining keksayish jarayoni va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy oqibatlarini // “Oila, xotin-qizlar va ijtimoiy hayot” elektron ilmiy jurnal. 2022 yil 6-son. – Toshkent, 2022. – 51-60-b.
3. Alijonov U.M., Satvaldiyev R.X. Aholining keksayish darajasini xalqaro indekslar bo‘yicha baholash mezonlari // “Oila, xotin-qizlar va ijtimoiy hayot” elektron ilmiy jurnal. 2022 yil 6-son. – Toshkent, 2022. – 61-77-b.
4. Xodjayev S., Sodiqov F., Rashidov SH., Nurullayeva U. Keksalari e‘zozlangan yurt. Risola. – Toshkent: “Mahalla va oila nashriyoti”, 2021. – 52 b.
5. Холостова Е.И. Пожилой человек в общества. – Москва: Социально-технологический институт, 1999. – 320 с.